

Mindful Transformation and Sustainable Mental Well-being through Yonisomanasikāra: A Buddhist Perspective from Myanmar

Khin Kyi Zin¹ Lin Lin Htet^{2*}

(1.Krirk University, Bangkok 10220)

(2.International Buddhist Studies College, Ayutthaya 13170)

Abstract: Every human being lives with both physical and mental factors, and both mind and body are constantly changing. In this day effected by psychological stressful, moral disorientation, and global instability, developing inner resilience has become a critical part of sustainable development. In Myanmar got the double crisis, Covid and a coup pushed the civilian to destroy their physical and mental health. All levels of people suffer from property, business and jobs lost during both crises. The worst one was losing their family members and migrants to domestically and international, including our families. We noticed that peace of mind and livelihoods can practice from the religion purpose. This research focuses on understanding how the appearance and disappearance of mind and body, through paying wise attention, can lead to the realization of Nibbana, with special reference to the Buddha's Dhamma in the Tipitaka. The study presents the factors that hinder yonisomanasikāra translated wise attention as the foundational approach to boosting mental quality and ethical consciousness. This study investigates the philosophical basis, methods and transformational outcomes of yonisanasikara in the context of both individual well-being and society sustainability. The methods can support peace-oriented behaviors values useful to substantiable living. It is not only contributed to inner sustainability but also meets the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with promote it, the varying states of attention in individuals, and the effects of wise attention in daily life. This research approaches Good Health and well-being, Quality of Life and Peace with modern sustainable framework based on ancient wisdom. While no one can change the aging body, paying wise attention is fundamental to training the mind to become stronger and more powerful. The importance of yonisomanasikāra in daily life is explored both theoretically and practically to more understanding of livelihood, to resilient

Author Biography:Khin Kyi ZinTom, Krik University, E-mail:khin.kyizin@krirk.ac.th, Research Field:education and management. Corresponding Author:Lin Lin Htet, Candidate, Ph.D in Buddhist Studies, International Buddhist Studies College

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from the suffer, adaptable in the new normal in the wider community and then minimizing harm to the environment.

Keywords: Mental health; Mindfulness; Sustainable Well-being; Buddhist Psychology

1. Introduction

Myanmar is faced the COVID pandemic and then political affair in most of the country regions. Many civilians lost their property, family members and business during these civilian war and Covid Pandemic, their mental effect and physically cannot acceptance of suffering and know about the impermanence of life. Today's world also has been devastated by the pandemic, as well as by the greed and anger of people. Therefore, not only physical aspects but also mental ones need to be reformed. Right thought can alleviate mental problems, which in turn can reduce physical pain. Those who seek a healthy body and a peaceful mind must understand the Buddha's Middle Way. The Buddha preached, "Oh Bhikku, there are two facts that can arise the right view." Namely,

Getting good advice and words from other people (Paraghotho) and

Paying good attention to (Yonisomanasikāro) ¹

Considering this Dhamma, the first one indicates making good friends and the second one considering everything positively and in a guiltless way. The first one is of the outside and the second one of the insides. These two facts are the first step of the Noble Eightfold path. To avoid misunderstanding, one needs to understand the middle way of the Buddha.

Those who have understood the middle way are those who have great attention to. Yonisomanasikāra is not philosophic speculation but reflection built on observation seeking to understand how things originate through condition.² Ayonisomanasikāra, one does not direct attention to the core or essence of a matter of phenomenon in order to understand its true nature but rather directs attention away from them.³ The term "yonisomanasikāra" is something we become familiar with from early childhood, and we grow accustomed to its meaning and significance. However, when it comes to practical application of yonisomanasikāra, there remains a lack of sufficient studies that provide clear guidance on how to effectively practice it.

¹ Kh., p.7.

² Ven. Xin-xing, *Wise Attention, Bodhi Bulletin Dhamma News from Bodhi Monastery*, November-December, 2005, p. 2.

³ Ven. Ratanak keo, *The Factors of the Wise Man in the concepts of Theravāda Buddhism*, Journal of Buddhist Education and Research, Vol. 4, No. 1 (January-June) 2018, p. 57.

In modern society, religious teachings, including the practice of *yonisomanasikāra* (wise attention), are often acknowledged but not practiced. This lack of mindfulness leads to neglect of their transformative potential. *Yonisomanasikāra* plays a crucial role in individual growth and societal development by fostering wholesome outcomes, even in adverse situations. Conversely, *ayonisomanasikāra* (unwise attention) can lead to unwholesome results, even in favorable conditions. This paper examines the types, benefits, and methods of cultivating *yonisomanasikāra* through Buddhist teachings, emphasizing its importance in minimizing unwholesome actions and promoting virtuous deeds in daily life.

The Objective of this study is to explore how the practice of *Yonisomanasikāra* (wise/reflection-based attention) contributes to mindful transformation and sustainable mental well-being from a Buddhist perspective, focusing on its understanding and application within the Myanmar context. The additional factors are to assess the perceived impacts of *Yonisomanasikāra* on sustainable mental well-being, particularly in post-conflict or socio-politically stressed contexts in Myanmar. To analyze the relationship between mindful reflection (*Yonisomanasikāra*) and the transformation of mental habits, behaviors, and worldviews. To contribute to the development of a culturally rooted, sustainable mental health model informed by Buddhist psychology. The most prefer objective is to compare the application of *Yonisomanasikāra* in traditional monastic settings versus modern mindfulness-based interventions in Myanmar.

2.Literature Review

This section highlights the major concepts reviewed and found to be of relevance to this study. It looked at the theories of Buddhist concept and interlink between *yonisomanasikāra* and core sustainable development goals for modern society. It also looked at impermanence life, uncertainty of karma and the role of Four Noble Truth effective to the sustainable development of three pillars, environment, social and economic of the effective area. It gave the background culture on individual to the community from the country. Moreover, the sustainability of mental well-being refers to better ethical decision-marking in their daily routine both family and organization to be better relationship or productivity in their business until to the country development.

2.1 Meaning of Yonisomanasikāra

Yonisomanasikāra is described as wisdom that enables one to think in a correct and proper way⁴, advertence (āvajjana) at the five-sense doors⁵ and at the mind door. Manasikāra is the very first stage of the mind's encounter with an object, and it holds the associated mental factors to the object. There are three types of manasikāra: Vīthipaṭipādaka, javanapaṭipādaka, and āramaṇapaṭipādaka. Vīthipaṭipādaka manasikāra is pañcadvārasena citta that arise mental process. Javanapaṭipādaka manasikāra is manodvāravajjanacitta that arise javana process. These two types of manasikāra are referred to in paḷi texts as yonisomanasikāra and ayonisomanasikāra (unwise attention). Āramaṇapaṭipādaka manasikāra is the manasikāra cetasika that arises object on citta. In some contexts, ñāṇa is also referred to as yonisomanasikāra. ⁶

The mental factor of manasikāra is important as it directly influences the development of wisdom (pañcaviññāṇa), and āvajjandve can result in either wholesome or unwholesome states of mind. These pañcadvārasena and manodvārasena associated with vitakka (initial application), vicāra (sustained application), adhimokkha (decision) and vīriya (effort), so can lead adverting the mind (āvajjana).

The desire for pleasant objects and arises from unwise attention (ayonisomanasikāra) which the two forms complete arising of craving. On the other hand, unpleasant sensory desire and, accompanied by ayonisomanasikāra, which the two complete give rises to Dosa. ⁷ To eliminate unwholesome states such as craving (rāga) and anger (dosa), one must work to remove ayonisomanasikāra. If one understands and reflects on the opposite of ayonisomanasikāra is yonisomanasikāra wholesome qualities will naturally increase and grow.

2.2 Types of Yonisomanasikāra

Understanding action and result of action upon them is the most fundamental form yonisomanasikāra. The concept kamma that good actions lead to prosperity, and bad actions lead to suffering is something that Buddhists are taught from childhood. However, because people only know about kamma without truly understanding it, they often find it easier to engage in

⁴ Kh., p. 8: paccatta samutṭhitā yonisomanasikārā cintāmayī paññā.

⁵ Mañis., p.382.

⁶ Ashin janakābhivaṃsa, သဂြိုဟ်ဘာသာဋီကာ (*Saṅgriuhbhāsāṭīkā*), p. 109.

⁷ A.I, p. 87.

unwholesome actions and harder to do good. Intention (cetana) is kamma. ⁸ Intention has the power to inspire and drive actions. When one's intention leads to good actions—such as wholesome body, speech, and mind—this creates good karma (kusala karma). If actions are motivated by good intention, one will experience the present, but if driven by bad intention, one will face hardship and suffering. The potential of intention is such that, when fully understood, it leads to wisdom (paññā) and knowing is saddhā. If one does not cultivate good intentions and right understanding, one will only bring suffering upon oneself. Reflecting upon these truths with the knowledge that "wrong intentions lead to suffering" is a clear form of yonisomanasikāra.

In addition to basic yonisomanasikāra, there are four advanced forms of yonisomanasikāra:

Reflecting on the five aggregates (khandhās) as impermanent (anicca),

Reflecting on the five aggregates as suffering (dukkha),

Reflecting on the five aggregates as non-self (anattā),

Reflecting on the five aggregates as foulness (asubha) ⁹.

These are considered higher levels of wise attention, leading to deeper insight into the nature of existence.

The practice of yonisomanasikāra revolves around understanding the impermanence (anicca) of all experiences, whether through the senses or the mind. Recognizing that phenomena arise and cease due to causes and conditions fosters clarity and detachment. This realization eliminates craving (lobha) and aversion (dosa), cultivating mental peace. Impermanence also reveals the nature of suffering (dukkha), which arises not from events themselves but from their transient and pressured existence. By reflecting wisely, one can discern the true nature of suffering and develop freedom from attachment to self (anatta), which arises from misunderstanding reality.

Yonisomanasikāra also involves contemplating the body and mind as impure, impermanent, and conditioned. Such reflection prevents emotional agitation and diminishes attachment to notions of "I" or "me." This practice requires consistent application of the five forms of wise attention and the cultivation of habits for mindful reflection. By systematically practicing Yonisomanasikāra, individuals can reduce craving, anger, and delusion (moha), achieving peace,

⁸ A. III, p.415: cetanāhaṃ bhikkhave kammaṃ vadāmi.

⁹ DA. III, p.778.

prosperity, and liberation from ultimate suffering.

2.3 The foundation of Merit is Yonisomanasikāra

In the realm of merit (kusala), there are donations (dāna), moral conduct (sīla), and meditation (bhāvanā) as the primary types of merit. Among these, the meditation merit (bhāvanā kusala), which includes vipassana meditation, can only be practiced effectively when one follows the teachings of the Blessed One (Buddha). Regardless of the type of meritorious action, all rightful merit is based on yonisomanasikāra and has its foundation in understanding the true causes and conditions. 10

The principle of yonisomanasikāra causes the unmanifested merits to come into existence. The merits that have already arisen also eventually fade or decline.¹¹ All meritorious actions are the result of non-neglectful mindfulness (appamāda).¹² Therefore, yonisomanasikāra is the noble cause for the arising of merit, and it is the essential quality for the development of wholesome actions.

The Buddha taught that the body is fragile and easily decays, like a clay pot. One must guard the mind, ensuring it is free from harmful influences, much like a fortified city. The enemy, which is ignorant (kilesa), must be overcome with the weapon of wisdom. Once victory is achieved, it must be carefully protected. One should not become complacent or careless in success. 13 This was the Buddha's teaching.

The rising of dawn is like the emergence of the sun—an essential precursor. Similarly, the correct understanding and practice of yonisomanasikāra by a bhikkhu is a necessary condition for developing the Noble Eightfold Path, which leads to the realization of the noble truths. It is a crucial step in this process.¹⁴ Understanding and practicing the correct way of directing attention is the first step on the path to the goal: achieving the state of permanent peace, Nirvana, which is the final goal for all followers of the Buddha's teachings.

2.4 Refining the Mind through Yonisomanasikāra

The ability to restrain oneself from unwholesome actions in order to maintain the quality of

¹⁰S.II, p.99: Yekeci kusalā dhamma sabbete yonisomanasikāra mūlakā.

¹¹A.I, p.13: yoniso bhikkhave, manasikaroto anuppannā ceva akusalā dhamma parihāyantī.

¹²S.III, p.99: ye keci, bhikkhave, dhamma kusalā kusalabhāgiyā kusalapakkhikā, sabbe te appamādamūlakā appamādasamosaraṇā.

¹³Kh., p.6: kumbhūpamaṃ kāyamimaṃ viditvā, nagarūpamaṃ cittamidaṃ ṭhapetvā, yodhetha māraṃ paññāvudhena, jitañca rakkhe anivesano siyā.

¹⁴S.V, p.32.

the mind is called morality (*sīla*). The ability to keep the mind stable and undisturbed is called concentration (*samādhi*). The clear understanding of the body and mind after reflection and insight is called wisdom (*paññā*). The mind is often quick to be swayed by unwholesome thoughts and slow to act when doing good. ¹⁵ It is swift and eager to indulge in what it desires, but it is good when it does not fall into attachment. When the mind is free from distraction, it can lead to wealth in terms of happiness and tranquility. ¹⁶ A mind that does not settle can lead to much harm and confusion. ¹⁷ The mind is not easy to tame; it can be hard to resist doing what is unwholesome, even when one knows it is bad. Conversely, it can also be difficult to act in accordance with what is good, despite knowing what is right. The mind is often fast-moving, capable of thinking quickly. While engaged in good actions, the mind can also dwell on unwholesome thoughts. It is a mind that can be unpredictable and hard to grasp. The mind is swift in both creation and destruction, constantly changing. Without proper discipline, the mind can even entertain thoughts that should not be entertained. Therefore, it is important to tame the mind and practice restraint. A mind that is not settled will only lead to more unwholesome consequences. A mind that is settled, disciplined, and in control is good for the practitioner's well-being.

To tame and refine one's mind, wise attention is an indispensable tool in the practice of settling the mind. Without wise attention, the mind cannot be calmed or settled. The situation of an unsettled mind without wise attention is likened to the verse: *idaṃ pure cittamacāricārikam, yeniccakam yatthakāmaṃ yathācukhaṃ, tadajjaham niggaheṣāmi yoniso, hatthippabhinnam aṅkusaggaḥoti.* ¹⁸ This refers to the *citta*, which, in its cyclical wanderings, follows its desires—just as one who is untamed follows their desires in the cycle of birth and death. Throughout the cycle of life, even today, the mind, thinking it is doing good, clings to the objects of desire that seem agreeable to the senses. In the same way that a shepherd, holding a leash, can control an unruly elephant, one must use the leash of wise attention to tame and settle their own wild, untamed mind. To settle the mind, wise attention is the key. Without it, the mind remains unsettled, just as an elephant will not be controlled without the proper reins.

¹⁵ Kh., p.17.

¹⁶ Kh., p.5: *dunniggaḥassa lahuṇo, yatthakāmanipātino, cittassa damatho sādhu, cittaṃ dantaṃ sukhāvahaṃ.*

¹⁷ A.I, p.5: *cittaṃ, bhikkhave, abhāvitaṃ mahato anathāya saṃvattatī*"ti.

¹⁸ Kh., p.131.

A mind that is not aligned with virtuous conduct tends to become defiled. When the mind becomes defiled in such a way, wisdom also weakens and diminishes. However, when the mind is correctly cultivated, bojjhaṅga will arise and progress. When these bojjhaṅga continue to grow, they lead to freedom from defilement, bringing the benefits of liberation and unshakable peace. As virtuous qualities expand, the mind becomes clearer and purer.

2.5 Methods for Cultivating Yonisomanasikāra

Intention, mindfulness, and wisdom lead to yonisomanasikāra. Ayonisomanasikāra arise from intention, delusion, and doubt. ¹⁹ The closest enemies that prevent virtuous growth without perceiving others' goodness are the weakening of intention, inability to decide based on one's own wisdom due to delusion, and the consequences of wrong views. The more distant causes include lack of mindfulness, aimless and careless thinking and actions, failure to understand the final goal of virtuous people, going astray from the path, and repeatedly making mistakes.

The bhāsāṭīkā Sayadaw explained that the presence or absence of the five components of the sampatticakka is related to the development of yonisomanasikāra.

Those who have performed good deeds in past lives, pubbeka katapuñña sampatticakka, and are able to act appropriately in accordance with the paṭirūpadesa of those virtuous ones. Those who the paṭirūpadesa sampatticakka are complete in the Sappurisūpanissaya cakka, which guided by their good parents, teachers, and relatives. These virtuous individuals also have a complete saddhammassavana cakka, which leads to their hearing the teachings of virtuous ones. Furthermore, those with the saddhammassavana cakka are complete in the attasamāpaṇidhi cakka, which they are capable of controlling both themselves and their thoughts. In this way, those who are complete in the attasamāpaṇidhi cakka encounter yonisomanasikāra in every sense and are constantly cultivating good deeds. However, those whose sampatti-cakka has become disturbed or fallen apart, and whose paṭirūpadesa has become flawed, will experience ayonisomanasikāra, resulting only in the accumulation of bad karma. Therefore, for those who cultivate good deeds, yonisomanasikāra is closely connected with the attasamāpannī-cakka, whereas ayonisomanasikāra stems from the disturbances in the far-off causes. ²⁰

¹⁹ A.IV, p.408.

²⁰ Ashin janakābhivamsa, သင်္ဂြိုဟ်ဘာသာဋီကာ (*Saṅgriuhbhāsāṭīkā*), p. 227.

Therefore, in our daily lives, whether it is from virtuous individuals or from books and teachings, we should strive to hear and study the saddhammasavana cakka and, through earnest effort, establish the attasammāpaṇidhi cakka firmly in our hearts. By diligently cultivating these qualities with determination and skill, we can develop and increase our wholesome deeds and advance in the practice of the Dhamma.

2.6 The Benefits of Practicing Yonisomanasikāra

When yonisomanasikāra is present, it can prevent various forms of suffering, such as untimely death, poverty, the breakdown of moral conduct, failure to attain desired positions, demotion from positions of authority, and suffering from the consequences of one's own mistakes. These are all results of unwholesome deeds that lead to decline and deterioration. On the other hand, yonisomanasikāra can also give rise to various forms of prosperity, such as achieving fame and recognition, maintaining wealth and resources, success in gaining high positions, and avoiding punishment or harm. These are all the results of wholesome deeds that lead to the growth and flourishing of good conditions in life. ²¹

Yonisomanasikāra not only facilitates the arising and fulfillment of the seven factors of enlightenment (bojjhaṅga) but also ensures their thorough development and completion. ²² Those who cultivate yonisomanasikāra can attain the fourfold path of a noble individual (sotāpanna, sakadāgāmī, anāgāmī, and arahant) and develop the six types of wisdom (ñāṇa).²³ A person who is complete in yonisomanasikāra will develop various qualities, such as joy, contentment, inner peace, prosperity, stability, correct insight, equanimity, the attainment of the noble path (āriyapariyāya), and the four noble fruits (āriyaphala). These are the qualities that such a person will experience and cultivate.²⁴

Yonisomanasikāra is the key to ending the factors that lead to defilements and the entanglements of dependent origination (paṭiccasamuppāda). As yonisomanasikāra develops, it leads to the Noble Eightfold Path, with right view (sammādiṭṭhi) acting as the light that dispels the darkness of ignorance (avijjā). This dispels ignorance, causing the cessation of defilements like greed, hatred, and delusion. As a result, the factors of paṭiccasamuppāda, including birth,

²¹ A. I, p. 13.

²² Ibid., p. 14

²³ S. V, p. 410.

²⁴ Vi. VII, p. 1366.

aging, and death, along with other forms of suffering, also cease. Therefore, yonisomanasikāra is crucial for ending the cycle of suffering and eradicating hindrances.

3. Research Methodology

“Methodology” implies more than simply the methods you intend to use to collect data. It is often necessary to include a consideration of the concepts and theories which underline the methods.

This study was managed with consideration of ethical principles. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement. Participants were informed of the study's purpose, their right to withdraw at any time, and the measures taken to ensure the confidentiality of their responses. All data were anonymized to protect participant privacy."

In this study, a combination of purposive sampling and simple random sampling approaches was used to identify potential respondents. Content analysis in qualitative research is carried out to analyze the data and to interpret the data. A semi-structured research instrument was created, and interviews were conducted in such a way as to enable each respondent to explore issues of particular interest and relevance to them. Each interview was, therefore, purposely designed to be unique. The study was conducted in Mandalay Divisions of Myanmar and was conducted from August 2024 until June 2025. The targeted research sectors are operational working sectors such as hospitals, schools, universities, supermarkets, mobile shops, cars showrooms and goods and services sectors which all are located in Mandalay and also the owners or managers are agreed and permitted to conduct the study. The targeted sectors must be individual, such as high school teachers, University lecturers, government departments employees, private sectors employees and SME owners. All personal interviews are recorded for data analysis. It's based on the level of difficulty and suffering of their experiences during both crisis and then classified yonisomanasikāra practice in their daily routine to get the sustainable mental well-being. We designed the following qualitative questions details as follows:

1. How do you understand the Buddhist practitioners and yonisomanasikāra in Myanmar?
2. How do individuals integrate Yonisomanasikāra into their daily routines and spiritual practices?

3.How does the practice of Yonisomanasikāra contribute to inner transformation and ethical awareness among individuals?

4.What are the lived experiences of individuals who apply Yonisomanasikāra in coping with stress, anxiety, or emotional challenges?

5.How is sustainable mental well-being conceptualized within the Buddhist communities of Myanmar?

6.What role does cultural, social, and religious context in Myanmar play in shaping the application and understanding of Yonisomanasikāra?

7.How can insights from Yonisomanasikāra be integrated into modern mental health or mindfulness-based practices to promote sustainable well-being?

4.Finding

This part of the chapter presents the finding and analyses the data obtained from the individual interviewees on the awareness and acceptance of yonisomanasikāra in Mandalay region, Myanmar. The data were extracted and analyzed according to the objective of the study.

1.Yonisomanasikāra as a Daily Ethical Compass Participants described Yonisomanasikāra as a tool for discerning right from wrong in everyday decisions. Laypeople associated it with mindful speech, consumption, and responses to conflict. It was commonly invoked before making moral choices, suggesting its integration with Sīla (virtue).

“Before I speak or act, I ask myself: ‘Is this rooted in greed or wisdom?’ That’s Yonisomanasikāra to me.” — Lay practitioner, Mandalay

2.Cultivation through Reflection and Meditation Monks and advanced lay meditators stressed intentional reflection during vipassanā meditation and post-meditative periods. Methods included reflecting on impermanence, cause-effect relationships, and dependent origination. Chanting and dhamma talks often emphasize cultivating yoniso manasikāra as a skill, not just a concept.

“Every session begins by turning the mind inward with wise attention. Otherwise, meditation becomes mechanical.” — University Lecturer, Sagaing

3.Mental Transformation Through Self-Inquiry Participants reported a shift from

emotional reactivity to thoughtful response over time. They described increased capacity for emotional regulation, tolerance, and inner peace as results of mindful reflection.

“I used to blame others for my suffering. Now I reflect: Where does this feeling come from? That change — that’s real transformation.” — Female meditator, Mandalay

4. *Yonisomanasikāra* as a Sustainable Mental Resource Practitioners viewed it as a renewable, inner resource — not dependent on external factors like wealth or environment. Especially in the context of political and economic instability, *Yonisomanasikāra* was seen as a stabilizing force.

“When the country suffers, we must look inward and stay steady. *Yonisomanasikāra* helps us do that.” — School teacher, Kyun Hla

5. Barriers to Practice Lack of education and doctrinal understanding limited deep cultivation among some laypeople. While many recognized “mindfulness,” the deeper reflective quality of *Yonisomanasikāra* was less understood in rural areas. Some associated it solely with monastic or advanced practice, suggesting a need for community-level Buddhist education.

6. Cultural Embedding and Support Religious festivals, community chanting, and teacher guidance help reinforce *Yonisomanasikāra* socially and ritually.

5. Discussion

Concept	Definition/Role
<i>Yonisomanasikāra</i>	Wise attention / appropriate attention — critical Buddhist mental factor enabling clarity, insight, and transformation.
Mindful Transformation	The inner shift in thought, emotion, and behavior through sustained awareness and reflection.
Sustainable-Mental Well-being	Long-term psychological resilience, contentment, and ethical harmony in life.
Myanmar Buddhist Context	Cultural and religious backdrop that shapes how practices like <i>Yonisomanasikāra</i> are taught, practiced, and lived.

Concept	Definition/Role
Ethical Living (<i>Sīla</i>)	Supporting domain that connects mental clarity with action and community values.

Table: Concept of keywords

This study showed how *Yonisomanasikāra* another word as "wise attention" or "systematic attention"—is understood and practiced by Buddhist communities in Myanmar, and how it contributes to mindful transformation and sustainable mental well-being. The findings suggest that *Yonisomanasikāra* is not only a meditative or doctrinal concept but a deeply lived practice that shapes how individuals relate to themselves, others, and the world.

1. *Yonisomanasikāra* as an Applied Cognitive-Ethical Process Consistent with the Abhidhamma framework, participants described *Yonisomanasikāra* as a key mental factor (*cetasika*) that guides perception, decision-making, and ethical conduct. Unlike mere concentration (*samādhi*) or passive mindfulness (*sati*), *Yonisomanasikāra* involves active discernment—"thinking in line with Dhamma"—which echoes the teachings of the *Satipaṭṭhāna Sutta* and *Majjhima Nikāya* (MN 2). This supports the idea that *Yonisomanasikāra* facilitates a transformation of consciousness through structured, intentional reflection.

2. Mindful Transformation Through Reflective Attention A recurring theme among participants was the inner shift from habitual reactivity to intentional awareness. This aligns with contemporary psychological models of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT), where conscious redirection of thought patterns plays a role in emotional regulation. However, *Yonisomanasikāra*, as described by Myanmar practitioners, goes beyond therapeutic mindfulness: it is a moral and existential lens, rooted in the Four Noble Truths and Dependent Origination (*paṭiccasamuppāda*). This deepens its transformative potential by linking personal insight with a broader soteriological goal.

3. Sustainable Mental Well-being in a Culturally Embedded Practice Participants emphasized that *Yonisomanasikāra* acts as a stabilizing force in the face of social, political, and economic uncertainty. In contexts of collective stress—such as post-COVID recovery or political instability—this practice enables individuals to find meaning and steadiness without relying on external control. This resonates with the Buddhist ideal of *santutthi* (contentment)

and modern sustainability discourses on inner development goals (IDGs). Unlike Western mental health models that emphasize pathology, Yonisomanasikāra fosters a proactive mental ecology that supports resilience and ethical harmony.

4. Knowledge Gaps and the Need for Buddhist Mental Health Literacy A significant barrier to deeper application of Yonisomanasikāra was limited doctrinal literacy, particularly among rural laypeople. While mindfulness is commonly promoted in Myanmar, the reflective depth of Yonisomanasikāra was less understood or often conflated with general religious observance. This finding suggests the need for culturally sensitive educational initiatives that frame Yonisomanasikāra not only as a monastic or philosophical concept, but as a practical mental skill applicable across all levels of society.

5. Cultural Anchoring and Implications for Mental Health Practices Myanmar's Theravāda Buddhist culture provides a rich ecosystem for the cultivation of Yonisomanasikāra—through temples, chanting, festivals, and teacher-disciple relationships. Yet, globalization and digital distractions may dilute these traditional supports. The challenge is to adapt Yonisomanasikāra-based practices to modern life without losing their ethical and spiritual integrity. Integrating Yonisomanasikāra into community mental health, education, and mindfulness programs could offer a culturally congruent and sustainable approach to well-being in Myanmar and other Buddhist societies.

6. Conclusion

To purify the mind, one must hold on to mindfulness and apply wise attention (yonisomanasikāra). By understanding and contemplating yonisomanasikāra, the wholesome qualities of the mind will grow and increase. To develop yonisomanasikāra, one needs good intention, constant mindfulness, and the wisdom to discern and reflect appropriately. Furthermore, by listening to the teachings of the Dhamma, and practicing loving-kindness (mettā), compassion (karuṇā), sympathetic joy (muditā), and equanimity (upekkhā), one can steadily cultivate wholesome mental states. In this way, without giving rise to unwholesome actions, the wholesome qualities of the mind will increase, and one can reach the true peace of Nibbāna, achieving the ultimate liberation and tranquility.

This paper has investigated yonisomanasikāra as a practical and transformative mental

discipline rooted in Buddhist philosophy. Most of people accepted that the personal development base on emotional balance and ethical awareness. The practice not only growth personal mental health but also builds the foundation for sustainable relationships, accountability leadership and peaceful coexistence. The finding points out that yonisomanasikāra contributes meaningfully to the inner dimension of sustainability, coordinate with global goals of mental health, education, and social harmony. As societies find out integrally strategies for post-pandemic recovery and ethical development, integrating contemplative practices like yonisomanasikāra into personal and organizational setting can get profound benefits.

Future research could explore its application in education, mental health care, leadership training. Finally, sustainability must begin within. As a result of the cultivation of mindful awareness and wise attention, individuals are better prepared to respond to the society with wisdom, compassion and purpose. The transforming is not only themselves but the systems they are part of.

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